

Full Court Bias: Media Relations and the Gendered Framing of College Basketball in Utah

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Abstract

This study investigates gender disparities in institutional media coverage of NCAA Division I men's and women's basketball programs at six public universities in Utah. Using feminist theory and the depiction and reception framework, 48 press releases—previews and recaps—were analyzed to identify differences in article length, narrative depth, multimedia inclusion, and promotional content. Results revealed that, while some universities favored men's basketball in both quantity and quality of coverage, others prioritized women's teams or showed more balanced approaches. Even where word count was equal or higher for women's teams, qualitative differences such as coach quotes and multimedia assets often skewed in favor of men's coverage. These findings highlight inconsistencies in how universities represent gender through internal communication and suggest that institutional media practices may unintentionally reinforce broader societal inequities in sport. The study calls for increased scrutiny of athletic communication strategies to promote more equitable representation of women's sports.

Keywords: gender equity, sports media, NCAA basketball, feminist theory, institutional communication

Sports are deeply woven into modern society, shaping personal development and cultural identity from an early age (Banschick, 2012). Collegiate athletics, governed by the NCAA, represent a crucial stage in this journey—not only for athletes but also for professionals in administration, coaching, and media relations (Coombs, 2024). While athletic performance often takes center stage, less attention is paid to how institutions communicate about their programs, particularly regarding gender equity. Media relations departments, responsible for

crafting official narratives, play a vital yet often overlooked role in influencing public perception of collegiate sports.

Despite progress in women's athletics, gender disparities in sports media remain pervasive. Female athletes are still frequently portrayed through lenses of appearance or personality rather than performance, reinforcing stereotypes and diminishing their legitimacy (Carpenter & Acosta, 2004; Shultz, 2016). These inequities may extend beyond mainstream media into

internal university communications. This study examines how NCAA Division I, state-funded universities in Utah—specifically Southern Utah, Utah, Utah State, Utah Valley, Utah Tech, and Weber State—represent men’s and women’s basketball through official press releases. Using feminist theory and the depiction and reception framework, the research explores whether institutional media relations practices uphold or challenge existing gender inequalities in collegiate sports coverage.

Literature Review

While limited research specifically examines how athletic media relations departments cover men’s versus women’s sports, broader scholarship provides vital context regarding disparities in sports media coverage, institutional priorities, and gender representation.

The Power and Priorities of the NCAA

The National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA) governs more than 1,100 colleges and universities, 100 athletic conferences, and 40 affiliated organizations (NCAA, 2019). It operates across three divisions, with Division I programs receiving the most visibility, funding, and media attention (NCAA, 2018). Financial incentives strongly influence the NCAA’s operations. In 2016, the NCAA extended its contract with CBS/Turner for March Madness broadcasting rights through 2032, adding \$8.8 billion to an existing \$10.8 billion deal (Sherman, 2016). Likewise, Power Five conferences receive enormous payouts from college football’s postseason, with the Big Ten alone earning over \$130 million in one season (Dosh, 2017).

These disparities extend to individual sports. Gaines and Nudelman (2017) reported that football programs in the Football Bowl Subdivision (FBS) generate an average of \$31.9 million in annual revenue, followed by men’s basketball at \$8.2 million. Women’s basketball ranked fourth, generating just \$1.8 million—less than men’s ice hockey and slightly more than men’s baseball. The lowest-earning sports were all women’s programs, such as volleyball, soccer, lacrosse, and softball. These figures reflect systemic resource imbalances that influence both media coverage and institutional support.

Title IX and Gender Equity in Athletics

Title IX of the Education Amendments of 1972 mandates that no individual in a federally funded educational program be excluded or discriminated against based on sex (Coombs, 2021). In athletics, this translates to equal opportunities to participate, equitable scholarship distribution, and access to comparable resources like coaching, facilities, and travel (Carpenter & Acosta, 2004).

However, Title IX does not mandate equal visibility. While women may receive equal opportunities to compete, the media attention they receive—both from external outlets and their own institutions—remains inconsistent. The ongoing disparity in media coverage and fan engagement reinforces the dominance of men’s athletics and raises questions about how deeply institutions commit to the spirit of gender equity.

Feminist Theory: Depiction and Reception

Feminist theory provides a useful lens to examine gendered communication in sports. The depiction and reception framework argues that individuals internalize ideas about gender through repeated media exposure. If men are routinely portrayed as stronger, more competitive, and more deserving of attention, these narratives become ingrained over time (Miller, 2002). These patterns are especially visible in sports media, which has historically framed male athletes as heroic and female athletes as secondary.

Feminist sport studies have gained prominence in communication research. Hovden and Pfister (2006) emphasized the importance of feminist scholarship in exposing and challenging the hierarchies embedded in sports media. Even legal mandates like Title IX have been misrepresented or misunderstood in coverage. Hardin et al. (2007) found that many journalists failed to grasp the law’s implications, often reinforcing outdated gender norms in their reporting.

Bruce (2016) noted that today’s female athletes navigate conflicting expectations—striving to be seen as legitimate competitors while also being expected to adhere to traditional standards of femininity. Internationally, some progress is evident. In Israel, a government department was created to advance women in sport (Galily, Kaufman, & Tamir, 2015). During the 2010 FIFA World Cup, more women assumed leadership roles, signaling efforts to challenge male hegemony in global sports (Clark, 2011).

Media Coverage of Women’s Sports

Scholars have long documented the underrepresentation of women in sports media. Reid and Soley (1979) analyzed *Sports Illustrated* content from 1956 to 1976 and found no significant increase in women’s sports coverage, despite rising female participation. More recent research confirms this trend. Women athletes are still frequently portrayed through lenses of attractiveness, emotion, or personal life rather than athletic performance (Shultz, 2016).

A study of *Sports Illustrated* by Brandt and Carstens (2005) revealed that their recurring “Beauty of Sport” feature often highlighted

women's appearance and personality over athletic merit. This portrayal reinforces harmful stereotypes and undercuts efforts to position women as serious athletes. These issues extend beyond sports; for example, Finnish Prime Minister Mari Kiviniemi faced similar framing, being simultaneously expected to appear both competent and traditionally feminine in media portrayals (Huovinen & Weselius, 2015).

Such coverage shapes not only public perception but also athlete behavior. Brandt and Carstens (2005), citing prior research, noted that women often switch sports, withdraw from programs, or underperform to meet societal expectations. These patterns illustrate how deeply media narratives can influence athletic identity and participation.

Research Questions

As Kian, Mondello, and Vincent (2009) noted, sports are a cultural cornerstone in American life, and media coverage significantly shapes perceptions of gender, institutional value, and athletic legitimacy. While much research has focused on external media, less attention has been given to how universities themselves frame gender through internal channels like media relations. This study uses a feminist theoretical framework—specifically the depiction and reception model—to examine how NCAA Division I, state-funded universities in Utah portray men's and women's basketball teams through official press releases. By analyzing institutional narratives, the research explores how gender is constructed by the very departments tasked with promoting student-athletes. To guide this investigation, the following research questions were posed:

RQ1: To what extent are men's college basketball teams being covered in the state of Utah as compared to women's basketball teams?

RQ2: What major differences, if any, exist in the coverage of men's and women's college basketball by media relations departments in the state of Utah?

RQ3: Do men's college basketball teams receive more attention than women's teams from their own media relations departments in the state of Utah?

The findings of this study aim to shed light on the role of internal media in perpetuating—or challenging—gender inequities within collegiate sports.

Method

This study examined 48 press releases from the media relations departments of six NCAA Division I, state-funded universities in Utah: Southern Utah, Utah Tech, University of Utah,

Utah State, Utah Valley, and Weber State. Private institutions such as Brigham Young University and Westminster were excluded. Each university provided four press releases for men's basketball and four for women's, consisting of two game previews and two recaps. To ensure fairness in comparison, the releases were selected from parallel matchups whenever possible.

The analysis focused on article length, structural elements, inclusion of direct quotes, and presence of promotional content. Word count served as a baseline for evaluating the level of coverage, while additional content such as multimedia or marketing tie-ins helped assess promotional emphasis. This approach aimed to identify patterns in how institutional media relations departments may differentially frame men's and women's basketball programs.

Results and Analysis

The primary goal of this study was to examine potential disparities in coverage between men's and women's basketball programs by NCAA Division I media relations departments in the state of Utah. While every institution surveyed exhibited some level of imbalance, the degree and form of disparity varied notably. University of Utah

Among the five institutions analyzed, the University of Utah displayed the most pronounced gap in coverage between men's and women's basketball. The average word count for press releases covering the men's team (the Runnin' Utes) was 1,024 words, more than double the 492-word average for the women's team. Structurally, both men's and women's releases shared a uniform layout—broken into sections rather than written in standard Associated Press (AP) format—but differences in content were clear.

Both of the men's recaps featured direct post-game quotes, lending the articles more depth and perceived importance. In contrast, only one of the women's recaps included comments from the head coach. This selective inclusion of quotes subtly reinforces the idea that men's games warrant more post-game analysis and commentary.

Interestingly, the women's previews did include promotional efforts, specifically color-themed giveaways ("Red Out" and "White Out"), where fans received free admission for wearing the designated color. This indicates some attempt to boost engagement with the women's program. However, the men's promotional content appeared more robust and financially backed. One men's preview highlighted the distribution of 11x17 posters and 5,000 branded

light sticks, suggesting a greater investment in production and fan experience. Additionally, both men's recaps featured embedded tweets and video content, demonstrating a deliberate and immediate multimedia push following the contests. Neither women's recap showed similar attention to digital media presentation.

Utah Valley University

Utah Valley University (UVU) displayed the second-largest gap in average word count. The Wolverine men's basketball team's press releases averaged 733 words, while the women's team averaged 500 words per release. The men's coverage not only had a higher word count but also included more descriptive game narratives. Curiously, the number of quotes skewed in favor of the women's team in this case: two of the women's releases included direct quotes compared to just one on the men's side. While this finding partially offsets the disparity in length, it does not fully compensate for the reduced depth and breadth of content overall.

Southern Utah University

Southern Utah University (SUU) showed a more modest but still present disparity in coverage. The average word count for men's basketball press releases was 761 words, while the women's releases averaged 600 words. The difference, though not as dramatic as at Utah or UVU, still suggests more comprehensive reporting on men's games.

The inclusion of quotes further illustrates this imbalance. Every men's release included direct commentary from the head coach, while only one women's release featured a quote. The routine use of coach statements in the men's coverage suggests a more intentional effort to humanize and contextualize those events, contributing to the perceived importance of the men's team.

Utah Tech University

Although Utah Tech University was not included in the primary analysis due to its transitional status from Division II to Division I at the time of the study, a preliminary review of its media coverage reveals patterns consistent with those observed at other institutions. Press releases for the men's basketball team at Utah Tech averaged 672 words, while those for the women's team averaged just 498 words—a disparity of 174 words. While not as stark as the gap seen at the University of Utah, this difference still suggests a tendency to provide more extensive narrative space and detail for the men's team. Similar to trends noted at Southern Utah and Utah Valley, the men's articles at Utah Tech tended to include more statistical breakdowns and game context, while the women's coverage was generally shorter and less robust. These findings further support the broader theme of gendered

discrepancies in media relations content, even at institutions undergoing structural and divisional transitions.

Weber State University

Weber State University (WSU) deviated significantly from the prevailing trend. The women's basketball team received longer and arguably more detailed press coverage than the men's team. On average, the women's press releases totaled 613 words, compared to just 390 words for the men's. This suggests that, at least at Weber State, media relations departments may be making a deliberate effort to balance—or even reverse—the typical gender gap in institutional coverage.

Despite the positive disparity in word count, other aspects of coverage remained limited. Only one release from each team included a quote, and only one of the men's press releases featured embedded video content. This points to a general lack of supplementary storytelling across both programs, even where word count may favor the women's team.

Utah State University

Utah State also ran counter to the broader pattern. In this case, the women's basketball team was covered more extensively than the men's team. The average word count for women's basketball press releases was 744 words, while men's basketball releases averaged just 406 words. The formatting was consistent across teams, with game previews broken into sections and game recaps presented in a traditional AP style.

Notably, none of the press releases analyzed from Utah State—regardless of gender—featured quotes, embedded video, or promotional content. This uniform lack of depth could suggest a more minimalist approach to media relations overall or reflect resource limitations within the department (Appendix 1). Still, the relative emphasis placed on the women's team in terms of length may indicate an institutional effort to provide more equitable coverage.

Conclusion

This study examined gender disparities in internal media coverage of NCAA Division I men's and women's basketball programs at six public universities in Utah. By analyzing press releases from athletic media relations departments, the research aimed to uncover how institutional communication practices may reflect or reinforce gender-based inequalities. Grounded in feminist theory and the depiction and reception framework, the study highlights discrepancies in coverage and offers a critical lens through which to evaluate institutional

commitment to equity. Ultimately, it serves as both a diagnostic tool and a call to action for universities seeking to promote fair and balanced sports representation.

RQ1: To What Extent Are Men's Basketball Teams Being Covered in the State of Utah Compared to Women's Teams?

The answer to this question is institution-specific rather than uniform across the state. While some universities, such as the University of Utah, Southern Utah, and Utah Valley, exhibited significantly longer and more robust coverage for men's basketball, others—namely Utah State and Weber State—offered more comprehensive coverage for their women's teams in terms of word count. The findings reveal that media relations coverage practices vary greatly by institution, and there is no consistent statewide trend that prioritizes one gender over another across the board. This suggests that disparities in coverage may be more reflective of individual department practices and staffing than a collective cultural norm across Utah's collegiate athletic landscape.

RQ2: What Major Differences, If Any, Exist in the Coverage of Men's and Women's Basketball by Media Relations Departments?

Significant differences were observed not only in the length of press releases but also in their content and presentation. In departments where men's basketball received more attention, coverage tended to include more post-game quotes, promotional tie-ins, and multimedia elements such as embedded tweets and video recaps. These components not only enrich the storytelling but also enhance fan engagement and elevate the public image of the team. In contrast, women's basketball coverage often lacked these supplementary materials and focused more narrowly on the game's final score or basic statistical summaries. While institutions like Weber State and Utah State challenged this norm in terms of article length, they still mirrored broader patterns of minimal enhancement in women's sports storytelling. These differences, though sometimes subtle, reinforce systemic disparities in institutional prioritization and media representation.

RQ3: Do Men's Basketball Teams Receive More Attention Than Women's Teams From Their Own Media Relations Departments?

The data revealed a more nuanced answer than initially anticipated. While the original hypothesis suggested that men's teams would universally receive more attention, the results of this study disprove that assumption. In fact, Utah State and Weber State both provided longer press releases for women's basketball teams, indicating that some institutions are making deliberate efforts to reverse or balance

traditional disparities. However, this is not true for all universities. In departments like Utah and Utah Valley, men's basketball clearly received more detailed and frequent coverage, suggesting that institutional values and departmental workflows still, in many cases, skew in favor of men's athletics. The presence of such variability reinforces the need for further examination into the internal decision-making processes and resource allocation within media relations departments.

Limitations and Future Research

While this study offers a valuable snapshot of gender representation in collegiate sports media, several limitations must be acknowledged. The most significant is the small sample size—only four press releases (two previews and two recaps) per team per institution were analyzed. This limited dataset does not reflect the full breadth of media coverage across an entire basketball season, making it difficult to generalize findings or identify long-term trends.

Additionally, the study did not control for variables such as opponent quality, game importance, or timing within the season, all of which may influence the depth or quality of press coverage. The analysis of promotional content and multimedia features was also limited and qualitative in nature. A more comprehensive, season-long dataset would offer greater clarity on institutional patterns and editorial decision-making.

The study focused solely on basketball programs at public universities within one state. Expanding the research to include additional sports, private institutions (such as BYU), or universities in other states would broaden the scope and strengthen the comparative value of the findings.

This is an evolving study that will continue to grow with additional data and analytical depth. Future research should examine a full season's worth of releases, incorporate quantitative coding of promotional and multimedia features, and consider resource allocation within media relations departments. Interviews with staff may also offer insights into the processes behind content creation. Ultimately, this research serves as a foundation for ongoing inquiry into equity, representation, and institutional responsibility in collegiate sports communication.

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